

Adjustable bottom discharge aperture in vertical centrifugal separator using extended screen-contacting paddles

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In a vertical centrifugal separator comprising a cylindrical perforated screen (22) surrounding a rotating paddle array (14), the bottom discharge zone (26) incorporates a variable aperture mechanism wherein one or more paddles of the lowermost paddle row are dimensioned to extend radially to the inner surface of the perforated screen (22), in contrast to the standard paddle clearance of approximately 25mm from the screen wall. Said extended paddles are individually rotatable about their longitudinal axis. When positioned horizontally, the extended paddles contact the screen surface and form a substantially closed bottom aperture. Progressive rotation of said paddles about their longitudinal axis creates a variable annular opening, enabling operator control of material retention time within the paddle interaction zone. The mechanism requires no separate valve components, utilizes the existing paddle mounting infrastructure, and the rotational actuation may be manual or automated. The variable aperture optimizes separation performance across feedstocks of differing density and moisture content.

Keywords: vertical separator, centrifugal dewatering, iris discharge valve, adjustable aperture, paddle geometry, retention time control

Author: Marc Vanderbeken, DryCake, De Panne, Belgium.

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